

Towards a Geocultural Vision of Postcolonialism: A Critical Analysis of Mahmood Mamdani's *Neither Settler nor Native: the Making and Unmaking of Permanent Minorities*

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Abstract

The paper relies on the insights of Mahmood Mamdani in his book: *Neither Settler nor Native the Making and Unmaking of Permanent Minorities*, to explore the geocultural vision on the relations between settlers and natives within different postcolonial states, to name a few, Israel, Sudan, and South Africa. The paper relies on the sources of the Anthropologist Mamdani regarding the postcolonial states and the two culturally different groups within it, to highlight the need for a geocultural vision of postcolonialism. This paper analyses the intercultural relations between settlers and natives. After examining the aforementioned relations, the paper suggests that intercultural dialogues and transcultural awareness and consciousness are needed in order to avoid genocide and violence episodes as described in Mamdani's work.

Key-Concepts: geoculture; postcolonialism; settler/native; intercultural dialogue

1. Introduction

Concepts such as globality, geoculture and transcultural discourse are overshadowed in postcolonial studies. Thus, the main focus of the latter is politics and historical events. Studying the aforementioned concepts is commonly perceived as transcending postcolonial-state-focused analyses. The present chapter aims to examine and analyse Mahmood Mamdani's (2020)¹ work entitled as: *Neither Settler nor Native: The Making and Unmaking of Permanent Minorities through Geocultural lenses*. According to Guamguami (2021)², geoculture refers to a combination of what is cultural and what is geographic via intercultural communication as well as international relations. Here, it highlights how cultural aspects (ideas, rituals, norms and objects) get distributed across geographical spaces. Wallerstein (2011: xvi)³ defined it as “a set of ideas, values, and norms that were widely accepted throughout the system and that constrained social action thereafter.” Thus, this concept is essential in Wallerstein's world-system analysis.

This paper uses the concept of geoculture to analyse the socio-cultural relations between settlers and natives within different postcolonial states. Unlike Wallerstein, the paper does not focus on the world-system but on postcolonial state as a geographical space in which cultural aspects get distributed and reconstructed.

Geoculture is comparable to geopolitics and geoeconomics as each term focused on a topic within a global framework (Guamguami, 2021). Little to no published studies was devoted to study post-colonial conflicts and national relations between natives and settlers within postcolonial states using geoculture. The aforementioned concept was widely used by public international and foreign policy makers in transnational discourses and reports, ethnic conflict resolution stakeholders to solve identity, ethnicity, religion and extremism related problems

and conflicts, and by Tink Tank theoreticians and practitioners to manage cross cultural issues between nations and people (Guamguami,2021).

It is of paramount importance to fill in the gap existing in postcolonial studies. Thus, the current study aims to highlight the idea that geoculture fits well with postcolonialism, the study is based on the work of Mamdani (2020) to shed the light on the unescapable connections between members of postcolonial states: majority and minority. This connection requires intercultural dialogue as well as transcultural consciousness that is based on appreciation of difference and a sense of responsibility towards **the Other**. Here, each group (settlers or natives) should deal with their other in the postcolonial binary opposition.

Mahmood Mamdani inaugurates his book by an interesting idea, which is, both modern colonialism and modern state were conceived of the creation of nation state. That is both nationalism and colonialism were co-constructed. Here, Mamdani highlights the process of creating a nation state and to what extent that process was similar to the one of the modern state or post-colonial state.

Mamdani (2020)¹ seeks to decipher the link between nation-states and the so-called post-colonial modernity. In doing so, he discusses two phases of the nation-state: the non-liberal and the liberal. Historically speaking, the non-liberal nation-state was born in Liberia in 1492, it was a state project that spotlights on the relations between minorities and majorities within its boundaries. These relations came to the surface thanks to the agenda of non-liberal nation-states that summed up in oneness, which obviously leads to ethnic cleansing and genocide processes specifically of Muslims and Jews. This phase of nation-states was known of its bloody religious wars (Mamdani,2020).

The liberal side of nation states occurred as a response to aforementioned religious wars. It was originated in the treaty of Westphalia in 1648. According to Mamdani, two key elements were emphasised on, with the born of the liberal nation state, which are: religious tolerance at home and reciprocal guarantee of

sovereignty outside its boundaries. To put it simply, tolerance was considered as the key to put an end to religious wars and terror and to guarantee civil peace within the nation state. Minorities within the nation states were tolerated to the extent that they were viewed as politically loyal and non-threatening to the national majority. Here, the liberal notion of the nation state succeeded to formulate permanent political identities for both majority and minority. However, unlike political modernity in Europe, colonial modernity tackled things differently. In colonies overseas, only people, who are seen as civilized, have the right to be tolerated (Mamdani,2020)¹ (see Obregón,2012)⁴. Others, the ones who are culturally different from Christian Europeans, had to be made civilized first before having the right to be tolerated. Thus, only the majority- the civilized- has sovereignty.

The mission of colonizers overseas was creating an avatar of modernity, a nation state, like the one existed in Europe, but ended up with an anamorphosis of it. This mission was entitled as “civilizing mission”. Unfortunately, this mission failed, the colonial modernity did not follow the footsteps of the modern states. Instead of liberal tolerance, colonies created a liberal conquest (Mamdani, 2020).

The new colonial method moved from adopting the civilizing mission as direct rule to indirect one. The colonizer imposed its laws, customs, educational practices, language and lifestyle which leads to natives’ resistance. The resistance opened the door for a new colonial method which is the indirect rule. The colonizer created different minorities instead of one, “each preserved under the leadership of a native elite. The native elite’s power was said to derive from custom, but it was the backing of the colonizer that was their true source of authority” (Mamdani,2020:03).

The differences that took place between religious groups were further expanded into civilizational differences between races and tribes. The previous distinction reminds us of the world of Samuel Huntington that categorized in terms of

religions. Separated into several tribes and races, natives faced and became conscious of new notions of otherness and difference among them. Despite the fact that the focus of Mamdani is political and historical in nature, but the presence of culture and economic motives embodied the colonial as well as post-colonial frameworks. In the same line, Mamdani states that:

Embracing political modernity means embracing the epistemic condition that Europeans created to distinguish the nation as civilized and thereby justify aggrandizing the nation at the expense of the uncivilized. The substance of this epistemic condition lies in the political subjectivities it affords. How does the subject understand herself? If she understands herself as a member of the nation, she is participating in political modernity. Colonized peoples lacked this subjectivity until Europeans foisted it on them, much as this subjectivity was foisted on Europeans themselves, at least in the early days of the nation-state. p.3

In his book, Mamdani explored the export and the distribution of the notion of different kinds of citizens and people in a given territory, sovereign and non-sovereign, from the United States to South Africa, Nazi Germany and finally to Israel. Mamdani argues that the United States was the initial blueprint in modern colonialism, and its political project was followed by South Africa, Nazi Hitler and Israel.

The present article explores the Geocultural face of postcolonial states and the Geocultural relation among the permanent settlers and natives resulted from it. The present chapter seeks to decode and highlight the cultural relations that existed between the two groups: settlers and natives, as mentioned in the book of Mahmood Mamdani, and to highlight the link between these cultural relations and the need for a Geocultural vision of postcolonialism.

2. American Indians and European Settlers: Geocultural Perspective

2.1. America as the role model in modern colonialism

In the first chapter of his book, Mamdani (2020)¹ tackles the Indian reservation in the US and considers it as a system by which modern colonialism was originated. Mamdani started with comparing two different historical narratives or discourses: one that considers the United States as far from being a colonial power or colony, and another one that considers it guilty of its indigenous people's genocide. He claims that US should rethink its history and start with considering itself as a colonial project at first, and a role model to the other colonial modernity's projects around the globe. The way the US dealt with Indians was copied by Nazis and South Africa later.

2.2. Otherness: Indians versus African American

Indians are different from African Americans in many ways. Pre-Colombian residents were called and viewed as Indians and not as natives. Here, the Indians were always regarded as aliens. The 1964 civil rights act excluded Indians in reservation, and it was until 1968 act that the Indians were included. However, the two acts are not similar as the 1964 act is constitutionally binding, whereas the 1968 act is only advisory. The idea of two different civil rights acts shows us the born of second-class citizens and third-class citizens (Mamdani, 2020)¹. Here, we can examine the difference and otherness in citizenship.

As mentioned above, the Indians were depicted as aliens, the uncivilised other. We cannot deny that the African Americans at that time were also aliens and others according to the perspective of European settlers. Significantly, Indians were colonized, Africans were dominated racially in terms of labour and slavery. Thus, racial and colonial domination are two different faces. The Indians were dominated colonially to take their lands, which go hand in hand with colonialism that means the conquest of territory and natural resources.

2.3. Indians and Two-State Solution

The two-state model was embraced not only when dealing with Indians in US, but it was also implemented by Israel when dealing with Palestinians. This two-state model solidified the idea of Mamdani (2020)¹ that America was the source of colonial modernity as the American model was embraced in different colonial projects later. That model leads to the emergence of Indian reservation system and the idea of separating Indians in a state without sovereignty. This is the territorial form of indirect rule. Thus, the European settlers stripped Indians from their lands in order to dominate them as colonized subjects and to minimise the political threats using a customary law. As Mamdani states:

the formation of the US political community comprised two broad developments. One was the coming together of settlers, both voluntary and forced, from Europe and Africa. The other was the legal designation of Indians as aliens without rights, in spite of their residence in US territory. As Chief Justice John Marshall put it in 1831, Indians belonged not to the American nation but to “domestic dependent nations.” This was a recipe for the creation of a permanent internal colony in the homelands. (p. 24).

In the aforementioned quote, Mamdani (2020)¹ indicates that settler is a political identity of both Europeans and Africans who came to US either voluntarily to start a new life and explore a new land and exploit natural resources, or forced as in the case of African Americans. The other permanent political identity was natives or minorities, they are Indians that were excluded from participating in sovereignty.

Nichols (1975)⁵ states that the former US president “Lincoln’s vision for the West carried with it the implicit doom of the Indians”, this vision leads to violence and genocide as well as bloody wars after his death. Quoting from Mamdani’s book: “The pale-faced people are numerous and prosperous because they cultivate the earth, produce bread, and . . . depend upon the products of the earth rather than wild game for a subsistence,” Lincoln explained. “This is the chief reason of the difference; but there is another. Although we are now engaged in a great war

between one another, we are not, as a race, so much disposed to fight and kill one another as our red brethren.” (Nichols (1975 :14-15)⁵ in Mamdani (2020)¹). The difference between settlers and Indians was omnipresent in terms of language, culture, lifestyle and race; however, the difference was a good excuse for settlers to treat the Indians in an inhumane way. But as mentioned in the quote above, Lincoln and Marshal believed that the coexistence between European settlers and Indians was impossible, which paved the way to another excuse for the two states model to take place. A non-sovereign state which belongs to Indians in reservations inside a sovereign state that belongs to the European settlers.

2.4. Geocultural Aspect of Settlers and Indians ‘Relationship

we cannot deny that European settlers and Indians are culturally and socially different, despite the definition of civilization that we have in mind. Mamdani (2020)¹ sheds the light on the cultural assimilation of Indians by European settlers. Here the goal of the settlers was to divest the natives from their cultural practices as well as their tribal identities. They believed that the assimilation was the only reasonable act through which they could help Indians to be more civilized as Europeans.

The history of customary law was full of misguided endeavours to culturally assimilate Native Americans, through policies ranging from the liquidation of communal Indian lands to direct prohibition of traditional languages and religions (Cornell,1988⁶; Pommersheim,1995⁷). The Indians were treated like wards, and were defined as subjects that couldn’t govern themselves. In the same connection, Justice Stanley Matthews’s majority opinion claimed that Indians were:

“to be subject to the laws of the United States, *not in the sense of citizens*, but as they had always been, *as wards*, subject to a guardian; not as individuals, constituted members of the political community of the United States, with a voice in the selection of representatives, and in the framing of the laws, but *as dependent community who were in a state pf pupillage*, advancing from the condition of a

savage tribe to that of the people who, through the discipline of labor, and by education, it was hoped might become a self-supporting and self-governing society”.(Ex parte Crow Dog 1883⁸, in Mamdani, 2020:52¹) (emphasis added by the author)

The aforementioned quote shows the portrayal of American Indians as savage and wards. the portrayal was an excuse to belittle the Indians and legitimise the claim that they need help to be more civilized and become a self-supporting and self-governing society. Unfortunately, the American settlers reneged on their promise as in the case of the five civilized tribes. These tribes were more civilised, according to the Eurocentric criteria, they inhabited permanent communities and they practised agriculture, they adopted many settlers’ practices that they found beneficial. These tribes were: *Chicksaw*, *Choktaw*, *Creek*, *Cherokee*, and *Seminole* (Mamdani, 2020).

The promises of self-governing and tribal sovereignty were not kept, no matter how the American Indians embraced the white culture and the ways of civilization, since both Indians and settlers had incompatible goals. Thus, there is no happy ending for all as the catalyst of this civilization mission was the Indians. The civilizing mission was a countersign for legitimizing the ethnic cleansing and genocides of Indians.

As I mentioned earlier, cultural assimilation took place to wash away the Indian culture and the practices of religious practices of Indians, and manifest itself in the prohibition of long hair on men. Bureaucratically, the BIA which is the Bureau of Indian Affairs proclaimed that:

Any Indian who shall engage in the sun dance, scalp dance, or any other dance, or any other similar feast, so called, shall be deemed guilty of an offense.

Any Indian who shall engage in the practices of so-called medicine men, or who shall resort to any artifice or device to keep the Indians of the

reservations from adopting and following civilized habits and pursuits, or shall adopt any means to prevent Indians from abandoning their barbarous rites and customs, shall be deemed guilty of an offence.⁹

As mentioned in the aforementioned announcements, the Indians were forced to abandon their spiritual and cultural practices because European settlers considered them as barbarous. Furthermore, Indians' names, the most elementary of cultural signifiers, were prohibited and replaced by English names. The roles such as farmers and ranchers were imposed on Indians in the style of European settlers. These cultural and spiritual practices as well as Indian names are significant in the lives of Indians, they provide them with a sense of belonging and emotional stability.

The Indian children were no exception, they brought together at reservation schools run by settlers or compliant Indians, or they were shipped away from reservations in order to separate them from their families and ingroups. These reservation schools' vision statement was, as Richard Pratt (1892)¹⁰ revealed, the founder of the Carlisle Indian Industrial School, "kill the Indian and save the man"(in Prucha 1973:261¹⁰). Unfortunately, this vision led to disastrous consequences that can be summarised using Huhndorf's (2001:201)¹¹ words, "heart-breaking experiences that drove Native children to commit suicide and to run away repeatedly."

These forced cultural appropriation and assimilation practices caused crisis instead of civilization. Because of both subjugation and isolation, Indians lost their sense of life and the rituals as well as the customs that were the building blocks to make sense of who they are and which community they belong to. Their sense of the self and the other became confusing. Taking the conception of Erikson (1968)¹² as a reference, there are two forms of identity: identity and difference. Firstly, identity takes the form of self-differentiation, or self-awareness, and a self of personal continuity. Secondly, difference derives from a

primary relationship between the self and the other which leads to an awareness of one's distinctiveness.

Accordingly, the American Indians lost their "indigenous self" since the settlers' attempt was to kill the Indians on them, and transform them into a so called civilised people. Here, there is no self-continuity, the pre-Colombian self, before the European settlement, was not associated with the self in question. The set of meanings, norms, rituals and cultural as well as religious practices has been replaced by other practices and rituals, that are disconnected from the material circumstances of the tribe.

Mamdani (2020)¹ states that there were substitutes, such as agricultural practices and Christianity, albeit, they were unfamiliar and irrelevant to the emotional and communal needs of Indians. As a response to this spiritual and cultural gap, Indians endeavoured to create some new practices that hearkened back to their old self, such as the Ghost Dance religion that emerged in the 1920s among Indian tribes in reservations. Thus, Ghost Dance brought Indians under single ritual which manifested a sense of unity and collective identity among them (Mamdani, 2020)¹.

Historically speaking, Indians 'conceptualisation of identity had taken a different approach, that is to say, they define identity as a cultural constraint. For them, the identity is not biological or racial but it is cultural. Significantly, cultural identity refers to those social identities that are based on cultural membership, cultural identity means identifying oneself with and accepting a larger cultural group, into which we socialise and share a system of symbols, traditions and values (Liu et al. ,2015)¹³. In the same vein, Ting-Toomey (2005)¹⁴ points out that cultural identity involves the emotional significance that is related to the sense of belonging to a given culture or a cultural group.

The conception of cultural identity adopted by Indians seems broader, and unlike the settlers, it is not subject to visible racial traits. Therefore, there were examples

of Indian tribes adopted “captured whites” and members of other Indian tribes. The outsiders were considered as members of the in-group and they share the same cultural identity.

The idea of cultural identity did not please the settlers. For this reason, they enacted laws that withdraw from the Indians the right to establish memberships, in accordance to their conception of cultural identity. The law defined membership according to blood quantum and replaced matrilineal descent by a patrilineal descent. The law aimed to minimise the groups of Indians and make the blood as a legal marker of Indian identity. These attempts minoritize the Indians and stick to them a permanent minority identity that become their future sense of self. Hence, the colonial settlement transformed the Indian self from an Indian cultural identity to a minority racial identity.

3. Understanding Native and Settlers: Apartheid South Africa

Mamdani (2020)¹ sheds the light on natives and settlers as political identities. He discussed the partial success of South Africa in destroying native and settler identities and creating a new one which is a survivor identity. Mamdani (2020)¹ defines them using a dichotomous discourse, he states that a settler cannot be a native, and the native is the creation of the settler. He added that “the native is the settler’s invented other: the settler claimed not only to be defined by history but be its marker, but at the same time stigmatizing the native as an unthinking captive of unchanging custom and a product of geography. My conclusion was that settler and native are joined; neither can exist in isolation. Should you destroy one, the other would cease to exist.” (p.144).

According to Mamdani(2020)¹, the South African experience was fruitful at the end, unlike the failed logic of Nuremberg and its Denazification. It did not respond to the extreme violence emerged from the conflicts between settlers and natives, by separating perpetrators from victims. Instead, it highlighted the issues that led

to violence and the needs of survivors. the South African recognised the settlers and natives' identities as political and historical ones, hence, changeable.

The imposed differences of race such as being African, Coloured, Indian, and white were overcome in order to destroy apartheid. Afrikaners also became part of the movement against it. Here, we can observe the building of a collective consciousness that accepted all the differences that put them against each other and decolonized laws so that they can be treated as equals.

The decolonizing process took place through breaking down the colonial distinctions between settlers and natives, and opening the doors for everyone to participate in the same political community, with settlers reconfigured as immigrants. Mamdani claims that what defined the settler was not their race, language and culture, but the law to which he was subject. This law, according to Mamdani (2020)¹, is named as civil law. Nonetheless, political systems, including laws, are cultural institutions. As Bourdieu (1977)¹⁵ stated that the culture is shaped according to its dominant economic and political system. Thus, each economic as well as political system imposes its culture. On the other hand, Dodd (1998)¹⁶ states that the outer layer of culture constitutes of several institutions and systems including religious, economic and political systems. These systems are products of culture. Both Bourdieu and Dodd agreed on the idea that there is a relationship between culture and the aforementioned systems, the question is which one is the product of the other. These cultural institutions played a major role in the transformation and the development of economic and political systems.

In the same token, Sun (2017:2)¹⁷ stated that: "Culture refers to the consciousness about life and social relations in economic and political activities in a society, including values, social consciousness and morality. Economic and political practices are the basis and container of culture, while thoughts about and understanding of economic and political practices are the main content of culture. It is difficult to build a culture in isolation of social reality. Culture has its own

particularity and will evolve with economic and political practices.” In the light of this definition of culture, culture shape the economic and political systems, but there is an interplay between them.

I believe that the enactment of laws is related to and part of culture, they are interrelated, so it is extremely hard to claim which one came first. The civil war in South Africa and the customary law in the United States created natives-settlers relationship and bloody ethnic cleansing as well as civil wars. In South Africa, race was considered as a political identity. Africans were put in the lowest position in the racial hierarchy, which is legitimised by a dominant culture of settlers. The political and intercultural conflict over territory and political power led to a discriminatory discourse over race and racial differences.

During the Apartheid period, South Africans were divided in terms of race. Mamdani (2020) found that this racial division is similar to what happened to American settlers and American Indians, and to Jewish and German after the Holocaust. The same process happened with the American settlers and American Indians Jewish and Germans. Racial groups were forced to live in segregated areas (NTULI,2012)¹⁸. These racial separations remind us of the two-state model: A sovereign state and a non-sovereign state belonged to natives, this model created new cultural differences that were added to the previous ones between natives and settlers. To put it differently, the separation means that each group will create another culture, different from the culture that they had before colonialism, that go hand in hand with their new political identity. Additionally, each group will construct an evil image about the other group.

Due to the segregation prior to 1994, Africans were free to go anywhere they liked and socialise with South African settlers, they had limited level of cultural knowledge about the other group, the same for settlers. The difference in social and economic classes and backgrounds made the gap between the two groups

grew wider. Additionally, Natives had to learn and speak the languages of the settlers, which solidified their superiority. (NTULI,2012)¹⁸.

This social and economic hierarchy “creates a ‘power matrix’ where different knowledge systems intersect, interact and compete. It is at this point of intersection that political dimension of interaction arises and power imbalances result” (Bradfield,2019:6)¹⁹. In the same vein, Grosfoguel (2007)²⁰ acknowledges that these knowledge systems not only reinforced through political and educational systems, but also through everyday interactions. Thus, the day-to-day socialisation and interactions guide and assist the spread and the legitimisation of post-colonial differences between settlers and natives, these differences became part of their reality and their sense-making process of their position in the post-colonial state. Edward Said (1979:12)²¹ also accentuated that colonialism is significant in the distribution of ‘geopolitical awareness into aesthetic, scholarly, economic, sociological, historical, and philological texts. These texts construct a consciousness of hierarchical differences that become a reference of everyday life practices of citizens.

4. Sudan: Tribal Sovereignty and Post-colonial Others

Mamdani tackles (2020)¹ the problem of Two Sudans in the post-colonial era: the Republic of Sudan, which its capital is Khartoum, and the Republic of South Sudan, which its capital is Juba. This separation is a result of the civil war, the South Sudan obtained its independence in 2011, whereas the new state, the South, has been witnessing conflicts between ethnic groups.

Mamdani (2020)¹ tried in this chapter to historize the intercultural conflicts between tribes in South Africa. The tribes, Dinka and Nuer, were not rivals before colonialism, instead, they were fighting to gain back their own new state. However, things changed with the colonial modernity, the British, in the early twentieth century, politicized ethnic boundaries and reconstructed cultural differences as tribal differences. Mamdani (2020)¹ commented on this issue

stating that the “inheritors of the colonial mentality govern as the British did, not as their ancestors did.” (p.196). Here, the Sudanese experienced a cultural and ethnic consciousness split, they adopted the British vision and start connecting to a given homeland with its traditional authority and its customary law.

The territory of what is now inhabited by “two Sudans” witnessed impressive cultural diversity for at least half of a millennium, but lately this diversity has been a source of tribal and intercultural conflict. Here, the British colonists tribalized Sudan, they created legal and physical boundaries between the tribes. These tribes that coexisted prior to colonialism despite their cultural differences. These actions were done so as to prevent the colonized from collaborating and developing solidarities between tribes.

Sudan’s several groups were conscious of their cultural differences in terms of religion, languages, agricultural practices, ways of life and political vision. The British took advantage of these differences and turned them into boundaries of authority and sovereignty, and they decided what political power that authority would take control of (Mamdani,2020).

The project, which highlights the lines of indirect rule of the colonialists, separated the Arabs from other groups through underlining the linguistic differences, and it separated the other cultural groups through ethnic differences. The north that was inhabited by the Arabs was more civilized and was the center of power, which left the South with no sovereignty. Thus, the South was further subdivided into several tribes at the level of territory (Mamdani, 2020).

This project put Arabs against Africans and African tribes against each other. Unlike the aforementioned relationships between settlers and natives in America and South Africa, the Sudan’s settler “against whom the native was opposed was not the colonizer; the British did not attempt settlement of the territory. Instead, the settler was the Arabic speaker in the North, whom the British understood to be an immigrant presence” (Mamdani, 2020:198). The creation of settlers in this

case required no actual settlers. This project imposed settler identity on Arabs and the native identity on African groups.

The Arabs embraced this settler-native dichotomy and maintained it after independence. They took advantage of the superiority that settler identity possesses. Influential thinkers and politicians position themselves as Arabs sought to define Sudan as an Arab nation, and Africans as inferior and uncivilized. In the same line, Ruay (1994:15)²² states that:” There is an exceptionally strong urge for Arabism among the Northern Sudanese people; everybody wants to be an Arab.” The Arabs highlighted the lines of the false history written by British, and choose to reconstruct their identity by distinguishing themselves as immigrants. This positioning solidifies the migration-centric discourse that assumes that meaningful change came with immigrants.

Identity ambiguity of Sudanese’s different ethnic groups was due to changes in the self-recognition, along with the false history and the emerging of settler political identity discussed thoroughly by Mamdani (2020). In the same vein, Prunier (2005:77)²³ tackled the issue of the Arabization process and the self-recognition of Northern Sudanese. He states that: “For the ‘Arabs’ at least, they are not completely sure of what and who they are. In the Sudan they are ‘Arabs’, but in the Arab world they are seen as mongrels who hardly deserve that name. They desperately strive for recognition of their ‘Arab’ status by other Arabs, who tend to look down on them-even using them the dreaded name of *abd* (slave) that they use for those more black than they are.”

The diversity of ethnic and cultural groups that emphasised Sudan in the past became a curse in the post-colonial era. Thus, the categorisation of Sudanese, coupled with the imposition of Arabism and Islam on African or Southern Sudanese, has led to a national identity crisis (Madibbo,2012)²⁴. This identity crisis expedited the emergence of armed conflicts, markedly, the civil war between the North and the south as well as the conflict in the Sudan’s Western

province of Darfur. Significantly, the Darfur's conflict was described as the first genocide of the 21st century (Madibbo,2012)²⁴.

This identity crisis can be viewed from two different perspectives. First, the essentialist perspective to identity accentuates the reason why, in some cases, the identity differences were the source of conflict arousal (Madibbo,2012)²⁴. Second, the instrumentalist perspective to identity encapsulates the strong association between marginalization and conflicts, which means that, the marginalised groups or minorities, the indigenous people, opted for political violence as genocide to show their discontent with inequality (Nordas, 2008²⁵ in Madibbo, 2012²⁴).

As Mamdani (2020) suggests in his book, Both Sudans should rethink the way they view themselves by washing away the falsified British portrayals of themselves and the others. They, as Sudanese, must appreciate their linguistic, cultural, and ethnic specificities, but they should also appreciate and tolerate the differences. Having a goal-oriented conflict over authority and recognition, they should first embrace a flexible mindset that emphasises new conceptions of Sudanese identities as being multiple, changeable, and fluid. The identity formation and transformation of Sudanese people had undergone several processes starting from colonialism to the emergence of a postcolonial state. These processes paved the way to the creation of settlers-native political identity. By deconstructing the dichotomous discourses that construct Sudanese identities, and unmaking permanent post-colonial settlers and natives, Sudan will adopt easily a multi-cultural model that cherish shared civic identity; no second-class citizens, and put the inclusion of permanent minorities in public sphere and institutions.

5. The Israel Palestine Problem: A Settler-Native Conflict

Mamdani (2020)¹ spots the light on the Isreal/ Palestine Question. He asserts that” Zionism arguably is the most perfected expression of European Political modernity in a colonial context” (p.250). He sheds the light on the differences

between South Africa that challenged the process of translating cultural differences into political ones, and the cultural identity into a political one, and Zionism that embraced this process. Accordingly, Zionism associated being a Jewish with being part of a nation. they linked the Jewish nation to Israel state. To wit, the vision of Zionism goes hand in hand with the doctrine of political modernity originated from Europe.

Zionism is a product of both oppression and enactment of European modernity. The nationalism that excluded Jewish from Europe as unwanted minorities, was a goal for Zionists later as they decided to have a state for their own. Zionist created their own nation-state, and they chose to be the oppressor and the nation, whereas the Palestinian were deemed to be oppressed, minority, and the other. The Jews are considered automatically a citizen of Israel, while the non-Jewish, who inhabited the land before the formation of Israel, cannot obtain the citizenship easily (Mamdani, 2020)¹.

The sweep of otherness does not affect the non-Jewish but also some Jewish groups. To put it differently, the acceptable form of Jewishness is Ashkenazim, who were the founders of the state. They considered themselves as more civilized, and they opted for civilizing the Mizrahim, Arab Jews. The Mizrahim were the second other for Ashkenazim. The former could not swallow the combination of being Jewish and Arab at the same time. Linguistic and cultural differences between the two Jewish groups let the fear washed over the Zionism and Israel state. Zionists were afraid that cultural similarities between Arab Jews and non-Jews and the possibility of a fruitful intercultural dialogue between the two, will hinder the settlement process (Mamdani, 2020)¹.

As a response to this issue, the Jews were subject to a civilizing mission, the same as American Indian one, they were de-Arabized. Here, the vision of Zionist is crystal clear, the cultural assimilation and the suppression of the Arabic language shows the absence of diversity and the focus on making non-Jewish minorities.

The story of Israel and Palestine's intractable political conflict began with the immigration of Jewish to Palestine. The Jewish **immigrants** presupposed that they are the natives of the Palestinian land because it is their home-land. Mamdani (2020)¹ retells the historical process of Israel formation, and he highlights the transformation of Jews from immigrants to settlers, and the conflicts that arose with the increasing number of settlements in the Palestinian lands. The natives have not accepted the Zionist project, and chose to fight for their rights and lands.

Similar to the colonial experience that was tackled throughout the present chapter, the Israeli /Palestinian experience is no exception. The Zionist project, which has been implemented by European Jews and the British Empire, is a colonial project that created permanent settlers and natives. Despite the claim that Jews are also natives, which makes them settlers who considered themselves as natives. In a similar vein, Mamdani (2020:266)¹ stated that "Israeli Jews may be considered returning natives, even if their return comes after two millennia. But if Jews are returning natives, Palestinians are natives who never left, who can trace their link to the land for the same two millennia, if not longer".

The returning natives reconstruct an identity that the land is its core component. They transform the identity they had when they were minorities in other nations into a religious and Israeli national identity. Their desire to have a state and nation for their own made them ignore the present of the natives who never left, which are the Palestinian, they believed that they inhabited their land, "a virgin land". In doing so, they followed the footsteps of colonial project and the tenets of the emergence of a modern state.

The conflict between Israel and Palestine is not only a political dispute over territory. It is an intercultural one. The acculturation of Arab Jews solidifies the representation of Arabs in the mind of Zionists. The fact that Arab Jews and Palestinians were bearers of the Arab culture was scary for European Jews. In their mind, having cultural and linguistic similarities between the two may lead to

intercultural dialogue and tolerance. Thus, they have to deal with two others (Mamdani, 2020)¹.

Structurally speaking, the Arab and Jews were perceived as binary according to the Zionist dichotomous discourse. This “strategic essentialism” was highlighted by Shohat’s (1999²⁶, in Shenhav&Hever,2012²⁷) essay “Reflections of An Arab Jew”. She asserts that her grandmother learnt in Israel to refer to the Jews using “we” and to refer to the Arabs as “they”. Consequently, the “Arab Jews” is contradictory, it is an oxymore (Shenhav&Hever,2012)²⁷. As I mentioned earlier, the de-Arabization of Jews took place as a stage of strategic essentialism. The two others should not be mixed, they should have two different identities despite the cultural and linguistic closeness. In the same line, Behar (2021)²⁸, following in the footsteps of activist authors as Abraham Serfati, Ilan Halevi, Abbas Shibliak, and Ella Habiba Shohat, he established the collective signifier “Arab Jews” using a three-fold justification, which are as follows:

1. “ “Arab” is a linguistic and cultural marker rather than a racial or religious one.
2. Pre-1950s Jews within the Ottoman and Arab Middle East have participated fully in the production and consumption of Arab culture.
3. Distinctions in the Middle East were commonly drawn internally between “Jews,” “Muslims,” “Christians,” etc., rather than between “Jews” and “Arabs.” “(Trailblazers section, 7th paragraph).

Yet, this conception of Arab Jews was unconvincing for European Jews. The process of identity transformation and the erasure of Arabic heritage took place through school systems and army, and by separating Arabs from Arab Jews in different towns (Nurieli,2006)²⁹.

The conceptions of otherness among Israelis sheds the light on the Geocultural aspect of colonial project and postcolonial states. The others for Israelis are Arabs, Palestinians, because they accepted the widely used term “European Jews”. Here,

we can say that Israelis, despite the differences of religion and faith with both the Europeans and Arabs, they chose to accept and embrace the European Identity as mixed with "being a Jew". Remarkably, the colonial mentality and Eurocentricity influenced the consciousness of not only the Israelis, but also indigenous and non-indigenous group in postcolonial states, which led to a geocultural consciousness split.

What I mean by a geocultural consciousness split is the non-continuity of the process of awareness of and reflecting on what is cultural, either one's own culture or others' cultures, that get distributed across the postcolonial state. This non-continuity is due to the transformation of cultural consciousness, the construction of new identities (settler-native, minority-majority), and the acculturation processes and the dominance of colonial culture.

6. Conclusion

In the present paper, I analysed and highlighted the intercultural aspects used in Mahmood Mamdani's (2020)¹ book: *Neither Settler nor Native: The Making and Unmaking of Permanent Minorities*, in order to underline the need of a geocultural vision on postcolonialism studies. The assembly of the three concepts will enable us to decolonise the colonial-oriented discourses and destroy the binary oppositions that based on marginalising the alterity and constructing permanent identities.

Mamdani calls for decolonizing the political which means erasing the majority and minority identities that define the tenets of the nation state. Mamdani succeed to historize these identities, which shows that they are products of power rather than nature. Nonetheless, A geocultural analysis is needed to investigate the distribution of culture, identity and cultural institutions in the postcolonial state, and the possibility of establishing an intercultural or cross-cultural communicative strategy that fit all the cases mentioned in the paper, otherwise

each case will need its own strategy that will go hand in hand with the specificity of the history and the current events of each post-colonial state.

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